

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 14.06.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.08.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (122), 1602-1614

Research Article /Araştırma Makalesi
10.5281/zenodo.17012447

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ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02brte405>

Nature and Design Relationship: Environmental Messages in Art Exhibition Posters

Doğa ve Tasarım İlişkisi: Sanat Sergileri Afişlerinde Çevresel Mesajlar

ABSTRACT

Today, art exhibitions make significant contributions to raising environmental awareness through their nature- and environment-themed content. Issues such as the climate crisis, environmental pollution, and species extinction have increasingly become central topics addressed in exhibitions. In recent years, exhibitions emphasizing themes of nature and sustainability have gained greater visibility, while artists and designers have developed creative approaches centered on environmental awareness. Visual design practices convey messages quickly and effectively, creating awareness among viewers. Poster designs also assume this function, contributing to the communication of environmental messages through a visual language and thus constituting the focus of this study as a powerful medium of communication. In this study, the theme of nature and sustainability in art exhibition posters is examined in terms of visual and content aspects. It aims to reveal the significance of these themes for the fields of art and design through examples of environmental message transmission. A literature review provided a theoretical framework by highlighting the reflections of the subject area on visual communication and graphic design. This study employs a qualitative research method based on a descriptive analysis approach to examine poster designs, which serve as powerful tools of visual communication, in terms of both form and content. The analyses focus on color and typography use, visual impact, employed metaphors, and intended messages. The scope of the study encompasses nature- and sustainability-themed art exhibition posters, with the sample consisting of five posters selected from recent national and international exhibitions. These posters were chosen to represent thematic relevance, visual diversity, and varied modes of expression. The findings emphasize the importance of color and typography, visual impact, and metaphor use in the communication of environmental messages, and propose recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of such messages in exhibition posters. Considering its current significance in the field of art and design, it is thought that future research on this subject will provide valuable contributions.

Keywords: Nature, Sustainability, Art Exhibitions, Poster Design, Graphic Design.

ÖZET

Günümüzde sanat sergileri, doğa ve çevre temalı içerikleriyle çevresel farkındalık oluşturmaya yönelik önemli katkılar sunmaktadır. İklim krizi, çevre kirliliği ve türlerin yok oluşu gibi sorunlar, sergilerde sıkça ele alınan güncel konular hâline gelmiştir. Son yıllarda doğa ve sürdürülebilirlik temasına vurgu yapan sergiler daha görünür hâle gelirken, sanatçı ve tasarımcılar çevre bilincini merkeze alan yaratıcı yaklaşımlar geliştirmektedir. Görsel tasarım uygulamaları, mesajı hızlı ve etkili biçimde ileterek izleyicide farkındalık oluşturmaktadır. Afiş tasarımları da bu işlevi üstlenerek çevresel mesajların görsel bir dille aktarılmasına katkı sağlamakta ve güçlü bir iletişim aracı olarak araştırmanın odağında yer almaktadır. Bu çalışmada, sanat sergileri afişlerinde doğa ve sürdürülebilirlik teması görsel ve içerik yönünden incelenmektedir. Çevresel mesajların aktarımına ilişkin örnekler üzerinden konunun sanat ve tasarım alanındaki önemini ortaya koymayı amaçlamaktadır. Yapılan literatür taraması, ilgili alanın görsel iletişim ve grafik tasarıma yansımalarını ortaya koyarak analizlere kuramsal bir çerçeve sağlamıştır. Araştırmada nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden betimsel analiz yaklaşımı benimsenerek, güçlü bir görsel iletişim aracı olan afiş tasarımları, biçim ve içerik yönünden irdelenmektedir. Analizler, renk ve tipografi kullanımı, görsel etki, kullanılan metaforlar ve aktarılmak istenen mesaj açısından gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırmanın evrenini doğa ve sürdürülebilirlik temalı sanat sergileri afişleri, örneklemini ise son yıllarda ulusal ve uluslararası sergilerden seçilen beş afiş tasarımı oluşturmaktadır. Bu afişler; tema uygunluğu, görsel çeşitlilik ve farklı aktarım biçimlerini temsil edecek şekilde belirlenmiştir. Analizler sonucunda renk ve tipografi, görsel etki ve metafor kullanımının çevresel mesajların aktarımındaki önemi vurgulanmış; sanat sergisi afişlerinde bu mesajların etkisini artırmaya yönelik öneriler geliştirilmiştir. Sanat ve tasarım alanındaki güncel önemi dikkate alındığında, gelecekte bu konuyla ilgili yapılacak araştırmalara katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Doğa, Sürdürülebilirlik, Sanat Sergileri, Afiş Tasarımı, Grafik Tasarım.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the theme of sustainability is becoming increasingly visible in the fields of art and design, and it is being used as a powerful means of expression that draws attention to environmental issues. In this context, art exhibitions are becoming important venues that highlight environmental problems. Poster designs for art exhibitions also stand out in this regard as effective visual tools that both convey information and raise social awareness. Such designs attract viewers' attention to environmental risks and foster sensitivity. These visual narratives, which contribute to the spread of a sustainable lifestyle culture for the future, have the potential to transform individuals' behaviors, showing that design is not only about aesthetics but also an educational, enlightening, and socially transformative tool. In this respect, sustainability-themed posters make the functional aspect of art and design visible in serving society, contributing to the process of producing creative solutions for today's and the future's problems.

Poster designs are among the powerful communication tools that emphasize environmental impacts. Frequently used in venues such as art galleries, which host painting, sculpture, ceramics, photography, installation, and performance art, these posters are often preferred with the aim of fostering ecological awareness in society and drawing attention to environmental issues (Şenyapılı, 2013, p. 123). Today, the weakening of the human connection with nature lies at the root of negative developments such as the advancement of technology independently from nature, unplanned urbanization, and overconsumption, which lead to ecological crises. In this process, design has become the most effective tool (Oduncu, 2020, p. 482). Nature-inspired designs and ecological art approaches contribute to rebuilding the relationship between humans and nature by raising environmental awareness. While art reflects the aesthetic values of nature, it also draws attention to ecological problems; design, on the other hand, plays a functional role in developing sustainable lifestyles that are in harmony with nature.

The increasing environmental awareness of consumers has directed their purchasing decisions toward products that do not harm nature and contain clean ingredients. This trend has led to the growth of the green market. However, companies' efforts to appear environmentally friendly in order to gain a share of the green market, even when they are not, have resulted in an increase in greenwashing practices. Especially, greenwashing efforts applied during the design phase highlight the responsibility of the designer (Gürsu & Pektaş Turgut, 2025, p. 123). In the age of sustainability, the designer assumes a role that is not only focused on aesthetic production but also sensitive to the environment and grounded in responsibility. Within the relationship between nature and design, environmentally friendly approaches are developed, conveying messages that raise public awareness. In this context, design becomes a strong carrier of environmental responsibility. Posters emphasizing nature enhance social awareness by bringing together the themes of sustainable living through the expressive power of art. Design practices prepared within the framework of the green market and sustainability, on the other hand, serve as significant communication tools that establish a link between environmental awareness and consumer behavior.

2. METHODS

In this research, a qualitative research method with a descriptive analysis approach was adopted. Poster designs, which serve as a powerful communication tool in the field of art and design, were evaluated in terms of both form and content. During the research process, a literature review was first conducted to examine the reflections of the concepts of nature and sustainability on art and design, thereby establishing the theoretical framework of the study. The population of the research consists of art exhibition posters with themes of nature and sustainability, while the sample is composed of five posters selected from recent national and international exhibitions: *What the Shore Brought*, *Touched by Humankind*, *Rhinos Back in Town*, *Waste Age*, and *Planet or Plastic?* These posters were selected based on thematic relevance, visual diversity, and different modes of expression, and were analyzed in terms of color and typography use, visual impact, metaphors, and the communication of environmental messages. In this context, the significance and impact of poster designs in creating environmental awareness were determined.

3. THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABILITY

Although the term ‘sustainability’ has only recently come into use, the fear of the depletion of natural resources and the instinct to protect nature date back to ancient times. Essentially, belief systems based on respect for nature and the preservation of what exists show that the concern for sustainability is a mindset inherited by humanity from its ancestors (Oduncu, 2020, p. 483). This situation indicates that sustainability is not a concept of today and that the human desire to live in harmony with nature dates back to ancient times. The concept of sustainability is defined as "the quality of causing little or no damage to the environment and therefore being able to continue for a long time" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2025). “Sustainability is the ability to meet needs without endangering the future, considering the requirements of both humanity and future generations” (Çelik, 2020).

Sustainable art is not just a passing trend; it is becoming a way of life for many artists. It is about questioning how we source materials, what impact these materials have, and how we can create without contributing to the growing pile of waste. Whether it is replacing traditional paints with natural pigments or using recycled materials to build sculptures, artists are finding new and innovative ways to align their creativity with their environmental values (ArtSloth, 2024). This approach reveals the power of art to create environmental awareness alongside aesthetic concerns. In this way, art becomes a form of expression that strengthens environmental sensitivity.

Like other living beings, humans have had to struggle to sustain their lives since their existence. The goal is survival; for this, humans act with the instinct to feed, shelter, and protect themselves against dangers. They succeed in meeting their basic needs. Then, they begin to recognize, learn, and experience their environment and conditions, and they continue to think in order to live under better conditions to sustain their lives. They try to live together with others, establish relationships with them, and improve their living environment (Saydam, 2016, p. 17). Over time, humans tend to produce, accumulate, and protect what they possess. In this process, sustainability emerges as a natural part of life and a way of thinking.

4. ECOLOGICAL REPRESENTATIONS IN ART AND DESIGN

Sustainable design and recycling, which have become prominent topics in the field of design in recent years, have also become sensitive areas of interest for artists. The transformation of waste materials and their conversion into something beneficial for society are considered meaningful solution proposals to today’s waste problem (Kayahan & Çevik, 2021, p. 5). Ecological representations in art and design are at the core of creative forms of expression that respond to today’s environmental crises. Artists and designers use visual representations as a tool to draw attention to ecological issues, invite people to rethink the human-nature relationship, and raise social awareness. These forms of representation critically interpret current issues such as sustainability, climate change, and species extinction by depicting nature. Art creates a space of intellectual and emotional interaction beyond offering the viewer an experience. Ecological representations reveal the transformative power of art and design.

At its core, any form of design that imitates and integrates with natural ecosystems, minimizing environmentally destructive impacts, can be referred to as eco-design. In this context, eco-design aims to provide a framework for an environmentally appropriate design and management system by integrating both anthropogenic and ecological values at relevant spatial and temporal scales (Shu-Yang, Freedman, and Cote, 2004, p. 102). Eco-art is a type of art that examines ecological issues, climate change, and natural phenomena. Eco-artists often use natural materials and sustainable practices to create works that spark change and draw attention to global environmental conditions. As environmental issues remain an urgent concern, eco-art has become an important tool for ecological activism and awareness (Artterra, 2025). As problems such as climate change and mass species extinction become increasingly impossible to ignore, interest in ecological issues and related themes within the art world has also grown. In this context, the concepts of 'ecological art' and 'eco-art' have gained increasing attention in recent years and have started to be used more frequently by various artists.

In ecological-themed works produced in the fields of art and design, a moral and functional discourse is distinctly developed with the aim of creating social awareness. While raising the audience's awareness of environmental issues, it also aims to present intellectual or practical action in the face of the current ecological crisis as a moral responsibility (Cucuzzella, 2021). The understanding of sustainability in art is increasingly spreading thanks to artists who wish to reflect the beauty of the natural world in their works. Art and sustainability can collaborate in various ways, whether through the artist's way of depicting their

surroundings or through the materials used in their works. Today, many artists have started to develop pieces and artworks that contribute to the environment (Green Petition, 2025).

Art galleries are important spaces where art meets the audience. They are defined as “establishments where art objects/works such as paintings (sketches/drawings, watercolor, pastel, oil painting, printmaking, collage), sculptures, ceramics, photographs, as well as jewelry, textiles, handicrafts, clothing, and increasingly furniture are exhibited and sold” (Şenyapılı, 2013, p. 123). Today, these galleries are seen to create environmental awareness, especially through nature and environment-themed exhibitions, and encourage viewers to think about sustainable living. Many artists also develop innovative solutions in art and design practices by using sustainable methods. “Design must integrate flawlessly and completely with the natural environment in physical, systematic, and temporal aspects” (Oduncu, 2020, p. 486). Therefore, design is a holistic process that should be shaped based on harmony, balance, and sustainability with the environment.

Art and design are powerful tools for conveying social messages. Visual expression conveys complex issues in a simple way. In this way, an emotional and intellectual connection is established with the audience. Issues such as environment, justice, and inequality become more visible. Design brings these messages into everyday life and creates awareness. Thus, art and design play an effective role in social change.

5. POSTER DESIGN AND THE POWER OF VISUAL EXPRESSION

Posters are an effective form of visual communication in conveying products, services, and messages. They provide effective communication with the power to reach large audiences in a short time. When typography, visuals, and logos come together in a poster, the impact of the message increases. The moment it attracts attention, it communicates with the audience and achieves its purpose. There is no magical formula for designing a good poster. Invention and imagination have always formed the backbone of the art of poster design. Posters that are compatible with their surroundings or create contrast, convey their message clearly, and strengthen their words with images, being understood, noticed, and arousing curiosity, are considered successful (Şenyapılı, 2013, p. 220). Symbols speak to us not by what they actually are, but by what they represent. An image refers to pictorial graphic elements that bring a design to life. Whether as the main focus of a page or a secondary element, images play an important role in delivering a message and are an essential part of creating a visual impression (Ambrose and Harris, 2013). Tevfik Fikret Uçar defines the word symbol (sign) as “a concrete form, an object, a sign, a word, or a gesture that represents a concept” (Uçar, 2004, p. 24).

Different ways of engaging with visual images, for example, define different kinds of spaces such as cinema and galleries. You do not applaud a film in the same way you applaud a sculpture, but even applauding varies depending on the type of film and the type of cinema you are in. This point, which concerns spaces and exhibition practices, becomes particularly important given the increasing circulation of images today; images repeatedly appear in all places, and these places mediate the visual impacts of images through certain viewing practices (Rose, 2023, p. 64). “Most of the signs and symbols we see today either go unnoticed or we are too accustomed to them because they are parts of a shared visual language and blend into the environment” (Heller and Anderson, 2023, p. 83). “The visual metaphor, with the word ‘metaphor’ being synonymous with the word ‘figure of speech,’ comes from the Greek meaning ‘to carry’ or ‘to transfer.’ The context is moved to a key point by substituting one idea or object for another. Visual metaphors can convey an idea by creating comparisons and connections between different objects” (Wigan, 2012, p. 48). In this context, visual metaphors leave a deep impression, a strong perception, and a lasting impact on the viewer.

While designing effective graphic indicators, fundamental principles such as contrast, rhythm, and balance can be used either together or separately. In design processes, while implementations are usually carried out with the aim of creating an impact on the target audience, the indicators intended to create the desired effect are specifically designed compared to other indicators. These indicators are obtained through design elements such as shape, image, color, texture, etc., which are made striking by applying various effects (Sayın, 2019, p. 30). “A sign is a two-sided unit of sound, image, etc.” (Barthes, 1979, p. 41). In this context, signs are perceived in five different ways: visual, auditory, olfactory, tactile, and gustatory indicators. For example, visual indicators used in poster designs are perceived through the sense of sight.

Typography plays a fundamental role in conveying the message effectively in poster design. However, there are two concepts that are frequently confused in this process: 'legibility' and 'readability'. Although these concepts are often mixed up, there is actually an important difference between them. "Legibility should not be confused with readability; readability refers to the characteristics of a piece of text or design that affect the reader's ability to comprehend it" (Gavin & Paul, 2017, p. 186). Colors also create a strong visual language in conveying accurate and effective messages. For example, using the color green in representing nature is one of the strongest visual codes associated with the environment. "Green is the color of nature, and therefore the color of life" (Causse, 2019, p. 156). "Colors can change how we perceive the real world and have the power to influence our behavior as well" (Causse, 2019, p. 54). In this context, colors influence the way we perceive the environment and our behaviors. Visual elements create an effective language, and colors, shapes, and symbols reveal the beauties of nature. Ecological issues find a place in the viewer's world of thought through visual representations. Poster designs are also powerful visual messages that make the impact of art and design on social change visible.

6. ANALYSIS OF ART EXHIBITION POSTERS CONTAINING ENVIRONMENTAL MESSAGES

In this section, art exhibition posters containing environmental messages are analyzed in terms of visual and content aspects. Beyond serving as a tool for exhibition promotion, these posters establish a strong connection between environmental themes and the audience. Posters addressing subjects such as nature, sustainability, and the human–nature relationship are examined with regard to thematic relevance, the use of color and typography, visual diversity, metaphors, and the conveyed messages.

MeshRu opened its doors on October 3, 2024, with the exhibition titled 'What the Shore Brought'. In the exhibition, Ahmet Rüstem and Hakan Sorar's work 'Foam' and Cansu Sönmez's work 'Nereids' explore the relationship between nature and humans. The exhibition invites art enthusiasts to reflect on the relationship between nature and technology (MeshRu, 2024). In the exhibition poster, natural elements and the theme of the shore are emphasized under the title 'What the Shore Brought'. In the visual structure of the poster, organic surface textures that appear to have been shaped by the effects of waves and wind draw attention (Figure 1). These textures represent the eroding power of the shore and the forms shaped by nature over time. The fluid forms in the visual reflect nature's own cycle and the traces carried by the shore. A simple color palette has been chosen for the poster. Natural wood and earth tones strengthen the theme of the poster. In addition, the geometric yellow shapes used add a modern feel to the poster and create a strong contrast, drawing the viewer's attention to certain points. The yellow color also gives the poster a lively and dynamic appearance. Typography has been designed to be quite clear and legible. A modern typeface has been chosen, and the title is emphasized in capital letters. A color difference is used among the names to create hierarchy, allowing the viewer's eye to comfortably navigate the poster. Overall, the poster presents a strong narrative that combines nature's own formations with a modern human interpretation. While the geometric elements used alongside natural textures symbolize the balance between nature and human intervention, the poster as a whole creates both an aesthetic and thought-provoking visual impact. In this respect, the poster stands out as a meaningful example for environmental themes and nature-focused art events.

In the exhibition space of 'What the Shore Brought', the artworks feature forms that evoke waves, water, and coastal elements (Figure 2). The installation shows how AI-generated textures merge with traditional materials such as ceramics and wood at the boundary where water and earth meet. This situation recalls creative periods in art history when craft and technology intertwined. The large installation with a wave-like form represents the movement of the sea. The blue tones used in the space evoke water and the sky, creating a natural atmosphere. Forms resembling sea plants, algae, and coastal stones stand out, appearing as abstract interpretations of natural elements brought by the shore. The glossy and fluid textures on the surfaces reflect the effect of water, reinforcing the theme of the exhibition. The blue and green tones create a look that harmonizes with nature. Soft color transitions and natural textures offer the viewer a calm and peaceful environment. These installations form a visual unity consistent with the design language of the poster, strongly reflecting the theme of nature and the shore both in the poster and the exhibition space.

Figure 1. 'What the Shore Brought' Exhibition Poster. MeshRu, 2024.

Figure 2. Views from the 'What the Shore Brought' Exhibition. MeshRu, 2024.

Kalyon Kültür met with art enthusiasts with the group exhibition 'Touched by Humankind' held at Taş Konak in Nişantaşı between September 17 and December 17, 2022. With this exhibition, Kalyon Kültür focused on the relationship between nature and art. Organized in parallel with the 17th Istanbul Biennial, the exhibition aimed to raise awareness of the damage caused by humans to nature through the works of Evan Roth, Félix Luque & Iñigo Bilbao, François Quévillon, Kevin Cooley, Persijn, Broersen & Margit Lukács, Sabrina Ratté, and Volkan Kızıltunç (Kalyon Kültür, 2022).

The poster titled 'Touched by Humankind' stands out as a powerful example among art posters containing environmental messages (Figure 3). In the poster, a dead fish is seen on the seashore with a plastic bag caught in its mouth. This image reflects themes of environmental pollution and human-induced ecological threats. A striking contrast is created between the foamy seawater, the sand, and the plastic waste. By juxtaposing natural textures with human-made pollution, the poster achieves a compelling visual narrative. In terms of color use, faded and natural tones close to nature have been preferred. The brown hue of the sand, the foam of the sea, and the gray color of the fish provide a harmonious natural palette, and this simplicity enhances the visual impact of the poster. For typography, a large and bold font has been used. The headline, placed at the top, is positioned to attract attention and delivers a clear and direct message through its typeface. The plastic waste shown in the poster serves as a metaphor that clearly represents the damage humans inflict on nature. The poster also creates a strong visual effect and aims to foster environmental awareness.

Evan Roth's work titled 'Landscapes' (left), displayed on the wall of Kalyon Kültür, is a striking example that addresses the impact of humans on nature within the context of the digital age. By drawing attention to the existence of Internet cables running beneath seemingly untouched remote landscapes, the work emphasizes the physicality of the digital world. The piece presents an artificial visual experience to the viewer with its nature landscapes covered in pink and red tones. The installation 'After Eden' by Margit Lukács and Persijn Broersen (right) is an example of an immersive installation that directly places the viewer into a natural environment. With dense forest landscapes extending along panoramic video screens and similar visuals projected onto the walls, the work creates a holistic atmosphere within the space. In terms of thematic relevance, the relationship between humans and nature is addressed through the act of observing nature. The work conveys a powerful environmental message that prompts reflection on the beauty offered by nature and how humans perceive it. Both works create a striking visual impact in terms of environmental messages and offer a narrative that questions the human-nature relationship (Figure 4).

Figure 3. 'Touched by Humankind' Exhibition Poster. Kalyon Kültür, 2022.

Figure 4. Views from the 'Touched by Humankind' Exhibition. Evan Roth's 'Landscapes' Work (left). Margit Lukács and Persijn Broersen's 'After Eden' Work (right). Kalyon Kültür, 2022.

The solo exhibition 'Rhinos Back in Town' by artist Özge Günaydın, which draws attention to endangered species and the destruction of our planet, consists of striking works that question the relationship between humans and nature. The exhibition poster addresses the relationship between city and nature with an ironic tone (Figure 5). In the poster, a large rhinoceros sculpture stands prominently in front of a modern cityscape. This visual presents a strong theme by depicting the unexpected presence of nature within an urban setting. The rhinoceros figure, positioned alongside the concrete structures of the city, highlights the conflict between humans and nature. In terms of visual diversity, the detailed surface texture of the sculpture forms a strong contrast with the modern buildings in the background. Natural brown tones and metallic grays have been preferred in the use of color, creating a balance between the natural and artificial elements of the sculpture and the city. In terms of typography, large and bold letters have been used; the headline is placed vertically on the left side of the poster, and the use of white color enhances readability.

The visual impact of the poster is quite strong; the unexpected placement of the rhinoceros figure within the city evokes curiosity and surprise in the viewer, delivering a thought-provoking message on both environmental and social levels. The rhinoceros sculpture serves as a powerful metaphor representing the unbalanced relationship between humans and nature, as well as the impact of urbanization on natural life. In this respect, the poster stands out as a notable example of environmental messaging, inviting viewers to reflect on the relationship between nature and the city.

The works featured in the ‘Rhinos Back in Town’ exhibition, which carry environmental messages, appear highly striking (Figure 6). The overall theme of the work focuses on nature and animal rights. In terms of theme relevance, the rhinoceros figure refers to the protection of nature and the right to life of animals. In terms of color use, green, orange, yellow, and red tones, as well as pastel and soft shades, stand out; these vibrant colors emphasize the tension between nature and danger. From a visual impact perspective, the work offers the viewer an energetic and dynamic composition. The curving patterns and flowing color movements carry metaphors referring to the natural cycle and ecological balance. The rhinoceros figure carries a metaphorical meaning as a unique and protected part of nature, delivering a message that highlights the beauty and fragility of natural life. The works in the exhibition convey a striking environmental message about the protection of nature and animals.

Figure 5. ‘Rhinos Back in Town’ Exhibition Poster. Nef Masterpiece Hall, 2020.

Figure 6. Views from the ‘Rhinos Back in Town’ Exhibition Works. Özge Günaydın, Nef Masterpiece Hall, 2020.

The exhibition titled ‘Waste Age’ was held in 2022 at The Design Museum in London (Figure 7). This exhibition was an important event that questioned how design can offer solutions to the waste problem and invited viewers to reconsider the concept of waste. The poster design titled ‘Waste Age’ focuses on the issue of waste and sustainable design, carrying an environmental message. In the poster, abstract forms resembling waste materials are highlighted. These visuals, created by combining different types of waste (plastic, metal, electronic components), are integrated with the text of the poster and designed to be placed within the word ‘Waste.’ This approach establishes an effective balance between typography and visual elements. The bright fluorescent yellow background quickly draws the viewer’s attention while also

serving as a warning about environmental crises. The typography, consisting of large and bold black letters, presents a simple and clear message, enhancing the poster's readability. The visual impact of the poster is quite strong; the vibrant colors and sharp contrast evoke both curiosity and awareness in the viewer, while the transformation of waste into artistic forms creates a thought-provoking visual. The question 'What Can Design Do?' featured on the poster stands out as a powerful metaphor questioning the problem-solving power of design. Overall, the poster serves as a striking example in terms of environmental messages, offering a visual narrative that invites viewers to reflect on waste and sustainability.

These three spatial images from the 'Waste Age' exhibition address the themes of waste, consumer culture, and circular economy through visual language and spatial arrangement (Figure 8). In the exhibition space dominated by fluorescent yellow tones, the phrase 'Waste Age' is repeatedly used to create typographic movement. This intense and alarming color draws attention to the urgency of environmental crises, while the graphics and data-based information on the walls aim to raise awareness among visitors. The section titled 'Precious Waste: Changing Our Minds About Value' invites viewers to reconsider the concept of waste, and the blue digital screen next to it visually illustrates the concept of circular economy through graphic design. This section, with its calm colors and simple typography, guides visitors toward an informative experience. In the section titled 'A Throwaway Culture,' the text on the wall explores the historical roots of consumer culture and waste habits, while the accompanying objects provide visual diversity. The spatial arrangement not only conveys information but also reflects waste and consumption issues through metaphors. In this regard, the exhibition presents an effective and comprehensive narrative in terms of environmental messages.

Figure 7. 'Waste Age' Exhibition Poster. The Design Museum, 2022.

Figure 8. Views from the 'Waste Age' Exhibition. The Design Museum, 2022.

The 'Planet or Plastic?' exhibition was organized as part of National Geographic's long-running awareness efforts against the global plastic waste crisis. The exhibition reveals the extent of plastic pollution while also highlighting innovators working to solve this urgent problem. Aiming to reduce the amount of single-use plastics reaching the oceans, the exhibition seeks to raise awareness among viewers about plastic dependency (National Geographic, 2019). Designed by the National Geographic Society, this exhibition is a global traveling event that has been showcased in many different cities. The exhibition's poster design can be considered a strong example in terms of conveying environmental messages (Figure 9). The poster features a striking visual of what initially appears to be an iceberg on the ocean's surface, but upon closer inspection is revealed to be a plastic bag beneath the water. In terms of theme relevance, the message of plastic pollution and ocean conservation is directly reflected. This design draws attention to the hidden dimensions of plastic pollution and strongly emphasizes the unseen impact of environmental contamination. The use of cold blue and gray tones reinforces the themes of ocean and ice, while also evoking a sense of a polluted atmosphere. The typography is simple and clear, with the question 'Planet or Plastic?' prominently highlighted in large, bold letters. Visually impactful, this poster masterfully adapts the iceberg metaphor to the plastic waste crisis, engaging the viewer both visually and emotionally. Overall, the poster stands out as an effective example of environmental messaging, offering a powerful visual narrative that invites viewers to reflect on plastic consumption and ocean pollution.

In the entrance area of the 'Planet or Plastic?' exhibition, the use of blue tones and the image of a sea turtle entangled in plastic waste strongly reflects the theme of ocean pollution (Figure 10). The sea turtle stands out as a metaphor symbolizing the threats of plastic pollution on marine life. The yellow frame, aligned with National Geographic's corporate color, creates a striking entrance effect. Overall, the space presents a strong visual impact and conveys a clear environmental message.

Figure 9. ‘Planet or Plastic?’ Exhibition Poster, 2019.

Figure 10. Views from the ‘Planet or Plastic?’ Exhibition, 2019.

7. CONCLUSION

With the global escalation of environmental problems today, the role of art and design in this context has become more significant than ever. Art exhibitions not only provide audiences with an aesthetic experience but also convey messages aimed at raising environmental awareness by drawing attention to ecological crises. In this regard, they invite individuals to reconsider their responsibilities toward nature and to develop awareness of sustainable lifestyles. Poster designs for art exhibitions stand out as effective communication tools in delivering environmental messages to broad audiences. The posters examined in this study communicate contemporary environmental themes—such as pollution, sustainability, plastic waste, ocean conservation, and consumption habits—through visual language. The colors used in these posters, particularly tones associated with nature such as blue, green, and yellow, represent natural balance, while the typography, with its simple, clear, and legible structure, has been observed to enhance the impact of the message. Strong metaphors, including animal figures, waste materials, and natural textures, foster both emotional and intellectual awareness in the viewer, thereby reinforcing the visibility of environmental issues.

Various recommendations can be made to enhance the effectiveness of environmental messages in art exhibition posters. First, the more creative and intensive use of metaphors can facilitate the establishment of an emotional connection with the audience, thereby ensuring a stronger perception of environmental issues. Careful planning of color and typography harmony will contribute to the transmission of the message more effectively, both aesthetically and functionally. The use of striking visuals that emphasize sustainable design practices may further increase the attractiveness of the message and serve as a call to action for the viewer. Additionally, projects developed through international collaborations can provide

environmental messages with a universal language. The integration of aesthetic concerns with environmental sensitivity by artists and designers will contribute to shaping a sustainable design approach for the future. In this context, the effective use of visual communication tools in fostering environmental awareness is of critical importance not only for the present but also for equipping future generations with a sustainable culture of living. The strong impact of poster designs on viewers can be regarded as a significant means of disseminating environmental awareness and promoting the adoption of sustainable lifestyles.

Educational initiatives also constitute an essential part of this process. Through universities, art and design departments, and workshops, raising designers with a strong sense of environmental responsibility will provide valuable contributions to research and practice in this field. Environment-themed workshops, course content, and interdisciplinary projects can equip students with a perspective that integrates both aesthetic sensitivity and ecological awareness.

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